

Collaborative Governance as a Strategy for Optimizing the Potential of Coastal Areas and Local Tourism: A Study in Tangerang Regency

Muzakir Tawil¹, Yulizar P Tawil^{2*}, Giska Mala Rahmarini³, Indra P P Salmon^{4*}

^{1,2} Department of Public Administration, Tadulako University, Palu, Indonesia

³ Department of Communication, Tadulako University, Palu, Indonesia

⁴ Department of Public Administration, Bhayangkara University, Surabaya, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This research aims to study collaborative governance strategy in order to solve gap problem between abundance of natural resources but not equal in local management and constrained social phenomenon. Some barriers like low capacity that happen in street level government and local population. It will be interesting because paradox occur in abundance of advantages and welfare opportunity but cannot make local society out of local downturn and poverty (vicious circle). This research background is slum area phenomenon, low arrangement of local infrastructure, and poverty around tourism object and then attempted to explain stakeholder role in order to solve the problem. The research held in Banten Province, especially in coastal area in Tanjung Pasir Village. The research methods performed with interview, observation, and documents study. Field result also analyzed by participation rural appraisal (PRA) and continued by SWOT analysis and coastal tourism development identification strategy. The result of this research is two strategic issue: at first, Tanjung Pasir Village has some tourism development triggers like Tanjung Pasir Beach, Crocodile Captivity Park, Tanjung Pasir Resort, crossing access tourism island, Mangrove Park, and Seafood Culinary; secondly, main problem in tourism development is in local capacity of human resources (especially in quality standard enhancement of tourism components and local empowerment). Based on the field result, it necessary to improve tourism development components like attraction, amenity (accommodation), accessibility, and ancillary. After it is done in strategic issue mapping, it also necessary to coordinating all of stakeholder in collaboration scheme to develop tourism area in Tanjung Pasir Village to make welfare society. The implication of this research are contribute in tourism developing strategy by Tangerang Regency Government.

KEYWORDS: Collaborative Governance, Coastal Resources, Tourism, Tangerang Regency

I. INTRODUCTION

Tangerang Regency is an area directly adjacent to the Java Sea Coast which is located in the north. Also, Tangerang Regency is directly adjacent to the City of Jakarta or is a buffer area for the capital area. Concerning the existence of a coastal area, of course, the existence of the Java Sea forms a characteristic of the area as a coastal area. Also, the characteristics of the coastal area have an impact on the opportunities for the existence of abundant marine potential and natural resources (SDA) in the Tangerang Regency. The Central Statistics Agency noted that in 2017, fisheries GDP grew above 7% and was higher than the national growth rate (5.07%) in 2017 (BPS, 2018).

Figure 1. Map of Territory and Fishery Potential in Tanjung Pasir Village
Source: Research Documentary (2019)

Collaborative Governance as a Strategy for Optimizing the Potential of Coastal Areas and Local Tourism: A Study in Tangerang Regency

The contribution of the fisheries sector is not directly proportional to the welfare of the local coastal communities in Tanjung Pasir Village. A study conducted by Nizar (2018) shows that the rate of economic growth in the Tangerang Regency in 2017 was in the range of 5-6%. This fact also affirms the phenomenon in Indonesia which states that the coast, which should be able to bring prosperity to people tends to be stagnant and marginalized (Satria, 2015). In Tanjung Pasir Village, the lack of welfare is viewed from several aspects, namely: first, from the social structure in the form of the low quality of human resources, namely 85% of the population only receives basic education and does not attend school (Monograph Desa Tanjung Pasir, 2018); secondly, from the environmental aspect in the form of coastal slums and tourism access as well as poor readiness for infrastructure arrangement (Tangerang Regent Decree No.050/Kep.47-Huk/2015), and; third, the people's economic income is still in the range of 50-100 thousand per day and is below the average UMK Tangerang Regency (Banten Governor Decree No.561/Kep.442-Huk/2017, accessed in 2018). Based on this, the strategy must be carried out in a comprehensive and interrelated manner. This linkage contributes to hindering the progress of the area, including in the development of local tourism which has been prioritized by the local government.

The main potential in Tanjung Pasir Village is fishery products (including seafood) and marine tourism. Both fishery and tourism products are well known and visited by local people in Tangerang Regency and outside such as Jakarta City. TPI data for Tanjung Pasir Village recorded that in 2014 and 2015 (accessed in 2017), the amount of fishery production reached 82,653 tons and 75,088 tons in one year. From field observations, there is no fish processing to be converted into durable products. For fresh fishery products, local people mostly sell raw and auction directly at the fish auction (TPI) in Tanjung Pasir Village.

Some of the tourist destinations that have been owned by Tanjung Pasir Village are Tanjung Pasir Beach, crocodile breeding, sugar cane milling site, Tanjung Pasir Resort, and fish and shrimp seed centers in which there is a mangrove garden embryo. From the researcher's observations, it shows that the tourism management in Tanjung Pasir Village seems inadequate both in terms of attractions, amenities, accommodation, and accessibility. Besides, this is also reinforced by a study conducted by Suharsono et al (2015) which concluded that the cleanliness conditions (waste problem) and tourism aesthetics at Tanjung Pasir Beach show shortcomings. The drawbacks are especially in terms of tourist attractions, equipment (public bathrooms/toilets), garbage disposal, crossing facilities, and other amenities. If it is managed seriously, then coastal tourism will be the main trigger in fostering the socio-economic conditions of the community. As disclosed by Spillane (1989) that tourism has the opportunity to have an impact on the welfare of the surrounding community, especially in access to employment and other fields.

Tourism growth is generated through the development of local characteristics in Tanjung Pasir Village, especially the combination of potential with local products. The aim is to attract local and surrounding communities to come to visit. As stated by Risanti (2010), an effort to attract tourists is by offering products at tourist locations. In the village of Tanjung Pasir, this interest is caused by seafood with prime quality, cheaper prices, and it is better if you have to buy marine products that have gone through the freezing process after being distributed in supermarkets and markets. However, as long as the exploration continues, the natural potential is limited to the sale of raw/salted fish and local culinary delights. For tourism, visitors' interest arises from the coastal panorama. The problem is the lack of management capacity both from human resources, infrastructure arrangements, and the environment around tourism.

The management of tourism in Tanjung Pasir Village has almost the same conditions as the management of natural resources, there are still obstacles and limitations. Some of the existing tourist attractions, such as Tanjung Pasir Beach, crocodile breeding, sugar cane milling site, Tanjung Pasir Resort, and fish and shrimp seed centers that are integrated with mangrove garden embryos, currently have a condition that has not been fully managed. In other words, some tourist attraction embryos can become the backbone of the progress of Tanjung Pasir Village but their development readiness is still low considering their conditions that have very little attention from the local community.

Other opportunities for the development of Tanjung Pasir Village are the plan to develop mangrove cultivation and the existence of resorts in the local area. For the local community, this is an opportunity for added value to increase the growth of local welfare. The combination of potential coastal resources with the support of nature conservation tourism is believed to bring about changes in the form of an increase in the socio-economic quality of the community in Tanjung Pasir Village. Also, the location of the mangrove park in Tanjung Pasir Village is integrated with Tanjung Pasir Beach, which is a development priority in the development program of the regional government's arts and culture center in Tangerang Regency. It's just that there are problems in the form of limited local human resources, low-quality management of tourism management from the community and village government, access to capital that has not been fully reached, and development priority plans that have not been fully implemented. The impact, even though the potential is abundant, has made the conditions in Tanjung Pasir Village tend to be stagnant so that it requires coping and management strategies through cooperation and collaboration between stakeholders. The main objective is to find solutions and strategies in dealing with the paradox of high coastal potential but not yet optimally managed.

Collaborative Governance as a Strategy for Optimizing the Potential of Coastal Areas and Local Tourism: A Study in Tangerang Regency

II. METHOD

To analyze the study, strategies and methods are needed during data/information collection, analysis, and preparation of results. The collection of data and study information was carried out through triangulation. The parties involved are the community, local government, regional apparatus organizations (OPD), as well as the views of experts or experts. To compile the manuscripts of the field results, qualitative methods were used which made the researcher act as a participant-observer who carried out the process of recording, recording, and observing (Ahmad, 2015). As a limitation, the study focuses on the potential for coastal and local tourism as well as management in Tanjung Pasir Village.

Figure 2. Research Scheme

Source: Keban (1999)

Data regarding field conditions (community, government, and experts) is obtained through the PRA method or participation rural appraisal (interviews, interviews, documentation studies, conducting observations, and FGD). The reason the author uses the PRA method is that the research conducted by the author uses a participatory approach that seeks to get the perspective of the local community from various community leaders (local strong man) and local government (street level government) who represent the perspective of local conditions which are then analyzed and synergized with planning efforts. (Mustanir et al, 2018). This perspective starts from the exploration of problems, trends, or community habits, as well as the needs of the community in the development of the village area. For government perceptions, analysis of the study and evaluation of regional planning documents (evaluation of regional development plan documents, implementation of stakeholders, and real conditions in the field) is carried out. From an expert perspective, it is in the form of synchronization of field observations (natural potential (SDA) and local/regional potential) and is continued in the form of design formulations in both programs and technical areas of observation development. Another analysis was also formulated through the FGD stage which brought together all interested parties in Tanjung Pasir Village, both in the context of the substance of marine fisheries, tourism, and regional development.

From all the previous findings, the SWOT analysis of the internal and external environment was then carried out. In the internal environment of Tanjung Pasir Village, several things were analyzed, namely: a). Coastal resources (especially fishery/marine and tourism potential); b). The tourism development strategy that has been carried out, and; c). The performance of local and tourism potential development. The assessment is carried out by classifying the aspects of whether it encourages or hinders development. For the external environment, a study was conducted on trends in the form of external political, economic, socio-cultural, and technological aspects that had an impact on local coastal development. From the external environment, various development opportunities and threats have been identified that need to be avoided. After the SWOT analysis is carried out, a synthesis is then compiled between the objectives and priorities as well as the strategy for developing the leading sectors. During the formulation of a leading sector development strategy, there are several important points in each sector that researchers must understand, namely:

- a) Strong legitimacy by local communities which is supported by previous policy documents (obtained through development consensus);
- b) Contribution to support economic opportunities, both at a local scale and outside the region;
- c) Harmonization (integration) in social, economic, and environmental aspects such as increasing economic growth, employment opportunities, equity, a stable environment, harmony with natural conditions, and improving the quality of life of the population;
- d) Physical potential support such as land suitability and ecological zones;
- e) Support from the demographic conditions of the local population, technology, and community institutions.

III. RESULT

Mapping of Strategic Issues and Analysis of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT)

The combination of marine potential and coastal morphology is a major strength for residents in Tanjung Pasir Village. So far for most of the local population, the sea and its wealth have become a source of livelihood for sustaining life. Apart from being used

Collaborative Governance as a Strategy for Optimizing the Potential of Coastal Areas and Local Tourism: A Study in Tangerang Regency

for consumption, marine products and other assets provide livelihoods through community businesses around the coast of the Java Sea. The business that is carried out starts from the sale of fish (both raw and ready for consumption), complementary goods needed to catch fish, fuel for ships, or in the form of services related to the coast and services such as tourism. In other words, the coast has its charm in creating sustainability and sustainability of life for the community. Not only aimed at local communities but also existing or businesses in Tanjung Pasir Village related to coastal potentials also attract people from outside the village to visit the village to enjoy the potential and wealth of the coast.

The problems of local coastal communities are lack of human resources, lack of capital as a result of limited income, as well as environmental and area arrangements that require further revitalization and development. Furthermore, the existence of these obstacles is both a threat and an obstacle to regional development. As a consequence as well as challenges that emerge a strategy that must be carried out is to map the conditions followed by improvising the roles between stakeholders and institutions. This role is intended to empower the community, open access to community capital, and carry out government obligations related to infrastructure development in coastal areas.

Table 1. SWOT Analysis of Tanjung Pasir Coastal and Tourism Resources, Tangerang Regency

Strength	Weakness
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Coastal geography; b. Coastal activity center; c. Activities at the fish auction center; d. Garden mangrove embryos; e. The Seribu island access point; f. Local community support. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Silting by the sea; b. Poor docking and breakwater; c. Marine abrasion and pollution; d. Lack of tourism infrastructure; e. Poor tourism awareness; f. Lack of empowerment of local institutions; g. Lack of partnerships with private institutions.
Opportunity	Threat
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. opportunities to integrate between several tourist points; b. Multi-stakeholder collaboration that allows implementation through program synergy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Distortion of the coastal environment; b. Transitions and distortions of coastal cultures and local communities; c. Land use transition.

Source: Field Observation (2019)

The coast and its resources are the main capital in the development of Tanjung Pasir Village. The beach panorama has also been able to become a trigger related to village tourist attractions. Without making significant maintenance efforts, people can enjoy very valuable marine products. The role of the community is only to maintain the cleanliness of the coastal and marine areas so that they can explore and process marine products. Another impact is providing income and revitalizing the economy through the existence of fish auction centers (TPI), fishing boat docks, and fisheries activities. This can also be seen from the efforts of the village community who open simple stalls, street vendors, lodging, fishing equipment, service businesses, and other businesses. This is not only for actors in coastal activities and TPI, but also increases income for local people who live around the coastal area.

Figure 3. Mangrove Plantation Tourist Embryos (left); Tanjung Pasir Beach (right)

Source: Field Documentation (2019)

Tanjung Pasir village already has existing tourism based on the marine panorama. So far, coastal tourism is quite in a demand, especially Tanjung Pasir Beach and the crossing access route to the tourist island (because the access is quite close) which has become an alternative tourist destination for local people and outside Tangerang Regency. As stated by Arianti (2016), superior

Collaborative Governance as a Strategy for Optimizing the Potential of Coastal Areas and Local Tourism: A Study in Tangerang Regency

sectors have great opportunities for regional and regional development, especially in improving the community's economy. This can also be seen during tourism management activities, where the community provides ferry and boat rental services to the Thousand Islands so that it has an impact on the contribution of income to the service provider community. Also, several tours that have been running have become a priority for revitalization and combined with a new tourism embryo, namely a mangrove garden that integrates with fish farming ponds. A growing issue is the existence of integration through the creation of a mangrove park as access to Tanjung Pasir Beach. This can be seen through the road design with a width of 5-6 meters that was independently built by the community and community leaders in the mangrove park area. The design of this road also shows the full support of the community for tourism development in Tanjung Pasir Village.

The low quality of human resources in Tanjung Pasir Village is seen from the level of education of the village community and the type of work. Based on the 2015 Tanjung Pasir Village Monograph Data (accessed in 2018), most of the population only received a basic education and did not attend school (5,413 residents or 85% of the total population). Also, from the aspect of work, most of them are fishermen and workers in the informal sector such as laborers, coastal fishermen, and do not work (there are approximately 5,261 laborers and fishermen or 83% and 871 or 13% of the population who do not work). The high proportion of laborers shows the fact that the community is very weak in developing local potential and it is difficult to optimize income from the coastal sector, especially in efforts to increase the added value of products. Besides, the lack of official management workers in the existing tourism sector indicates that the community's ability to manage tourism is very low and conventional.

In the framework of sustainable development, the environment is an aspect that must be considered. The condition in Tanjung Pasir Village concerning the environment is the existence of a slum area of 3.06ha (Tangerang Regent Decree No: 050 / Kep.47-Huk / 2015 concerning the Determination of Housing Areas and Slum Settlements in Tangerang Regency). This area is also included in the vicinity of access to tourist sites and is quite disturbing when it is passed by people visiting several tourist points. Also, the infrastructure around the service area is very bad. From the observations made, there was silting around the docking of the ship and the breakwater began to break down. The impact is that the activities of the fishing community are disrupted when sailing and anchored when fishing due to the mud that settles on the edge of the pier. Besides, there are also impacts in the form of pollution, decreased quality of risk, habitat disturbance, and the threat of wildlife, and coral sedimentation (Gladstone et al, 2013; Hasler et al, 2008).

Figure 4. Degradation on the Coastal Edge of Tanjung Pasir
Source: Field Documentation (2019)

Slum area problems and the low quality of local human resources also have an impact on the welfare of the community in Tanjung Pasir Village. The high potential of marine and fisheries that is owned is difficult to optimize as a characteristic of the village given the limitations, especially in the management and manufacture of local products. Through the observations and triangulation conducted by researchers on local stakeholders, the government, several residents, fishermen, and a study of local government documents, it was noted that residents' income ranged from 50-100 thousand per day. If calculated, the local residents' income ranges from 1.5 to 3 million rupiah per month. The highest income is indeed quite close to the minimum wage standard (UMK) in Tangerang Regency which is around 3.6 million rupiah per month (Governor of Banten Decree No.561/Kep.442-Huk/2017, accessed in 2018). However, this income makes it very difficult for the community to set aside some of the material they have as capital for developing coastal natural resources. In other words, government intervention and parties outside the local community are needed to be able to open access to capital and empowerment within the framework of developing the potential of fisheries and marine natural resources.

The existence of several existing tourist points along with activities in one village is the main development potential aspect for Tanjung Pasir Village. The success trail around tourism itself is shown by the existence of a balanced relationship between supply and demand (Gunn et al, 2002). The study of the carrying capacity at Tanjung Pasir Beach shows the feasibility of the number of visitors on Tanjung Pasir Beach with a total of 162 people in one day (Muflih et al, 2015). This is also found from the information from the management community that tourists at Tanjung Pasir Beach range from 150 people to 200 people. This condition certainly provides opportunities for further development concerning tourism management in Tanjung Pasir Village.

Collaborative Governance as a Strategy for Optimizing the Potential of Coastal Areas and Local Tourism: A Study in Tangerang Regency

Role Sharing Strategy in Coastal Resources Management and Tourism

Based on a regional policy perspective, Tanjung Pasir Village is a promotional area as well as designated as a priority for regional tourism destination development. This priority was designed through the establishment of several programs in the Tangerang Regency, including the development program for the arts and culture center and tourism, the Coastal Community Development Movement (Gerbang Mapan), and the Rapid-Growing Strategic Area Development Program. As a consequence of several programs, during its implementation, the program involved several regional apparatus organizations (OPD) in the form of regional development cooperation. Some of these OPDs include the Bappeda Tangerang Regency, Spatial Planning Office, BPMPTSP, Regional Secretariat, Fisheries and Maritime Affairs Office, Youth Sports Culture and Tourism Service (Disporabudpar), Cipta Karya Service, and Department of Agriculture, Animal Husbandry and Food Security. Overall, each OPD has its main duties and functions during potential and area development and has been determined in the development program plan, mapped as follows:

Table 2. Stakeholder Mapping

Level	Institution	Role
National Government	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Ministry of Industry; 2. The Ministry of Trade; 3. The Ministry of Agriculture; 4. The Ministry of Cooperative and Small & Medium Enterprises; 5. The Ministry of Public Works and Public Housing; 6. The Ministry of Agrarian Affairs and Spatial Planning; 7. The Ministry of Environment and Forestry; 8. The Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy; 9. Maritime Affairs and Fisheries; 10. Women's Empowerment and Child Protection; 11. Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Region, and Transmigration 	As an institution that provides a legal basis and a foundation for development in the fields of housing and settlement development, fisheries and maritime affairs, community business, tourism, development of supporting infrastructure, poverty alleviation, and so on.
Province	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Marine and fisheries service institutions; 2. Agricultural and livestock service institutions; 3. Bina marga and spatial planning agencies; 4. Forestry and plantation service institutions; 5. Tourism and cultural institutions; 6. Industrial and trade service institutions; 7. Water resources and settlement agencies; 8. Cooperatives and micro, small and medium enterprises. 	
Regency	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Labor affairs service institutions; 2. Youth service institution, sport, culture, and tourism; 3. Bina marga and natural resources service institutions; 4. Spatial planning service institutions; 5. Housing, settlement, and funeral services institutions; 6. Cooperatives and micro, small and medium enterprises; 7. Fisheries service institutions; 8. Industrial and trade service institutions; 9. Water resources and settlement agencies. 	As an executor, facilitator, and person in charge of development projects in the fields of housing and settlement development, fisheries and maritime affairs, community business, tourism, development of supporting infrastructure, poverty alleviation, and so on.
Local	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tanjung Pasir Village Government; 2. Local Communities (home industries group, farmer group, fisherman group); 3. Tourist spot management team. 	As a target group as well as an indicator of the success of programs developed by the government As a development catalyst in seeing the core of the problem and formulating the main strategy in development

Source: Analysis (2019)

The focus and strategy in the management of coastal and tourism resources in Tanjung Pasir Village are based on a harmonious planning concept. By adjusting the vision and mission of Tangerang Regency, the emphasis on development is to improve the

Collaborative Governance as a Strategy for Optimizing the Potential of Coastal Areas and Local Tourism: A Study in Tangerang Regency

socio-culture, economy, and the environment, and this is also in line with the concept of sustainable development which emphasizes the harmonization of socio-culture, economy, and nature or triple-p, namely people, profit, and planet (Stren et al, 1992). In other words, people are defined as human improvement along with socio-cultural aspects; profit is defined as the benefit from the point of view of economic welfare, and; the planet is defined as nature that must be preserved and maintained in quality. The socio-cultural aspect is an aspect where the community can improve the quality of life through better education and health. Concerning the potential of the coast and tourism in Tanjung Pasir Village, the assumption is that there is a link between improving the quality of life in the form of encouraging empowerment and increasing human resources in Tanjung Pasir Village.

Tangerang Regency does not yet have a policy or regulatory review related to tourism. However, concerning tourism and the economic welfare of the community, a reference that can be used is Law Number 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism, to be precise in Article 4 of the law which substantively states that one of the objectives of holding tourism activities is to increase economic growth and prosperity. Public. On a local and regional scale, both the Tangerang Regional Government and local communities in Tanjung Pasir Village want a change for the community, especially when it is associated with the paradox of high regional potential but has not been able to significantly improve community welfare.

The urgency of the natural and environmental aspects is very high concerning the sustainability of ecosystem life and living places. However, this is often underestimated due to overly pursuing economic impacts without taking environmental impacts into account. One of the preventive efforts to protect natural and environmental aspects is to increase the capacity of the community and educate people in sustainably conserving nature. Also, tourism destination areas should be encouraged to continuously monitor the impact on the built environment, such as the level of cleanliness or land conversion.

Monitoring the development of tourism areas that has been carried out in general, is through the presence of the number of tourist visits or visitors through the recording mechanism of airports, ports, or other posts where the tourist community comes. These conditions only represent numbers and have not been able to provide an assessment aspect of the conditions of tourism and what strategies will be used in advancing the tourism area. Another aspect that is very potential in assessing tourism performance, such as recording more in-depth visitor profiles, such as origin, travel patterns, expenses, and tourist satisfaction levels is very important information to find out which market segments will visit later and this must be developed. This can also be used to estimate the revolving funds at the destination and make it efficient so that tourist visitors get the impression that the tourist area can provide quality at an appropriate price. Increasing the management capacity is also very important because it will ensure progress and determine the accountability and effectiveness of development. Moreover, based on regional autonomy regulations, tourism development in the regions is one of the duties of the regional government.

IV. CONCLUSIONS.

Optimization of coastal potential, local welfare and independence, and aspects of livelihoods that are more of a focus in the collaborative scheme to build Tanjung Pasir Village. The essence of the problem in Tanjung Pasir Village is in the form of a paradox between the abundance of maritime potential that is owned but is constrained by various socio-economic and environmental obstacles. Another problem is that the low quality of management results in low investment in Tanjung Pasir Village. So far, the existing marine and tourism potential has become the trigger and the backbone of the local community's livelihood. Another embryo is the existence of a mangrove forest which will be integrated as an entry route to Tanjung Pasir Beach and is expected to become the icon of Tanjung Pasir Village. However, the problem is the limited human resources, tourism supporting components, and poor infrastructure conditions have become obstacles so that there is no level of trust from outside to participate in investing in developing the existing potential, both in terms of marine and tourism resources.

Based on the results of the study through related methods, it is important to formulate strategies in the form of improvements in terms of improving the quality of local human resources both and shared values in the form of social capital in the community during the management of the potential of marine and tourism natural resources; access to micro capital and technical guidance (empowerment), particularly relating to modern management of coastal areas and utilization of their resources; implementation of coastal environmental conservation, an arrangement of area infrastructure, and revitalization of the environment so that the community can immediately create more potential areas, and; fully realize the role-sharing scheme between stakeholders, either vertically or horizontally. Seeing the current conditions, the urgency that exists is that there is a need for cooperation from various parties, including the community, community organizations, government, and other stakeholders to collaborate, share roles, and work together during the development of the coastal area in Tanjung Pasir Village. This effort is carried out through the implementation of both established development programs and other innovations.

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Collaborative Governance as a Strategy for Optimizing the Potential of Coastal Areas and Local Tourism: A Study in Tangerang Regency

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